

List of Selected Studies

Code	Authors	Year	Title	Conference/Journal	Key Focus	DOI
SP01	Mumford et al.	2023	Combining a legal knowledge model with machine learning for reasoning with legal cases	International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law (ICAIL)	Case Prediction	10.1145/3594536.3595158
SP02	Metsker et al.	2021	Application of machine learning metrics for dynamic E-justice processes	The 28 th Conference of Open Innovations Association (FRUCT)	Legal Assistance	10.1088/1742-6596/1828/1/012006
SP03	Wang et al.	2019	Using case facts to predict accusation based on deep learning	The IEEE 19th International Conference on Software Quality, Reliability and Security Companion (QRS-C)	Case Prediction	10.1109/QRS-C.2019.00038
SP04	Huang et al.	2021	Intelligent Recommendation of Legal Articles Based on DPCNN with Capsule Model	The International Conference on Computer Information Science and Artificial Intelligence (CISAI)	Legal Assistance	10.1109/CISAI54367.2021.00180
SP05	Freire et al.	2023	Exploratory Study of Data Sampling Methods for Imbalanced Legal Text Classification	International Conference on Hybrid Artificial Intelligence Systems	Data Clustering	10.1007/978-3-031-40725-3_10
SP06	Tian et al.	2018	K-means clustering for controversial issues merging in Chinese legal texts	Legal Knowledge and Information Systems	Data Clustering	10.3233/978-1-61499-935-5-215
SP07	Mohan & Nair	2022	Sammon Quadratic Recurrent Multilayer Deep Classifier for Legal Document Analytics	Computers, Materials & Continua	Data Clustering	10.32604/cmc.2022.024438
SP08	Zhu & Zheng	2021	Based on Artificial Intelligence in the Judicial Field Operation Status and Countermeasure Analysis	Mathematical Problems in Engineering	Court Productivity	10.1155/2021/9017181
SP09	Wu et al.	2020	Subject event extraction from Chinese court verdict case via frame-filling	2020 IEEE International Conference on Knowledge Graph (ICKG)	Data Extraction	10.1109/ICBK50248.2020.00012
SP10	Sil et al.	2021	Intelligent approach for automated argument based legal text recognition and summarization	Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems	Legal Assistance	10.3233/JIFS-189867
SP11	Xu et al.	2019	Case facts analysis method based on deep learning	Web Information Systems and Applications	Case Prediction	http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-30952-7_11
SP12	Roksandić et al.	2022	Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence and its use by Law Enforcement Authorities	2022 45th Jubilee International Convention on Information, Communication and Electronic Technology (MIPRO)	Crime Prevention	10.23919/MIPRO55190.2022.9803606
SP13	Kleinberg et al.	2018	Human decisions and machine predictions	The Quarterly Journal of Economics	Legal Assistance	10.1093/qje/qjx032
SP14	Ren et al.	2022	Ontology-based and deep learning-driven method for extracting legal facts	Electronics Journal	Data Extraction	10.3390/electronics11121821
SP15	Rodolfa et al.	2020	Predictive fairness to reduce misdemeanor recidivism	Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency	Crime Prevention	10.1145/3351095.3372863
SP16	Pah et al.	2022	The promise of AI in an open justice system	AI Magazine	Court Productivity	10.1002/aaai.12039
SP17	Demertzis et al.	2023	Secure and Privacy-Preserving Blockchain-Based XAI-Justice System	Information Journal	Court Productivity	10.3390/info14090477
SP18	Dai et al.	2021	Improved CBSO: Distributed fuzzy-based adaptive synthetic oversampling for imbalanced judicial data	Information Sciences Journal	Data Clustering	10.1016/j.ins.2021.04.017
SP19	Wang et al.	2019	Hierarchical matching network for crime classification	42nd International ACM SIGIR Conference	Crime Prevention	10.1145/3331184.3331223
SP20	Brugger et al.	2023	MultiLegalSBD: Multilingual Legal Sentence Boundary Detection Dataset	Nineteenth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law	Data Extraction	10.1145/3594536.3595132
SP21	Song et al.	2023	AI-enabled legacy data integration with privacy protection	Journal of Cloud Computing	Data Extraction	10.1186/s13677-023-00500-z
SP22	Han et al.	2022	Legalasst: Human-Centered Machine on Enhancing Court Productivity	Information Sciences Journal	Court productivity	10.1016/j.ins.2024.121052
SP23	Gatti et al.	2023	Mining Information from Legal Sentences in KlonDike	Proceedings of the Seventh Workshop on Natural Language for Artificial Intelligence (NL4AI 2023)	Data Extraction	https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3551/paper16.pdf
SP24	Weber et al.	2024	LegalWriter: Intelligent Writing Support for Legal Case Writing	CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	Legal Assistance	10.1145/3613904.3642743
SP25	Le et al.	2024	R2: Recall & Ranking Framework for Legal Judgment Prediction	IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing	Legal Assistance	10.1109/TASLP.2024.3365389
SP26	Bozdag et al.	2024	Measuring and mitigating gender bias in legal language models	ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data	Bias Mitigation	10.1145/3628602

SP27	Singh et al.	2024	Machine Learning Applications in Criminal Justice	2nd International Conference on Intelligent Data Communication Technologies and the Internet of Things (IDCIoT)	Crime Prevention	10.1109/IDCIoT59759.2024.10467221
SP28	Park & Kim	2023	Intelligent electronic monitoring supervision system	The 14 th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC)	Crime Prevention	10.1109/ICTC58733.2023.10393682
SP29	Lee et al.	2023	LeArNER: Few-shot Legal Argument Named Entity Recognition	International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law	Case Prediction	10.1145/3594536.3595144
SP30	Qin et al.	2022	Comparison of pre-trained language models for Chinese legal document classification	The 5th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Big Data (ICAIBD)	Data Clustering	10.1109/ICAIBD55127.2022.9820466
SP31	Benatti et al.	2024	Gender Bias Detection in Court Decisions	ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency	Bias Mitigation	10.1145/3630106.3658937
SP32	Wang et al.	2018	Modeling Dynamic Pairwise Attention for Crime Classification	The 41st International ACM SIGIR Conference	Legal Assistance	10.1145/3209978.3210057
SP33	Luo et al.	2017	Learning to predict charges for criminal cases	Proceedings of the 2017 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing	Legal Assistance	10.18653/v1/D17-1289